

Process Skills Assessment using Instant Evaluation Strategy for Instilling Confidence in Pre-Service Biology Teachers

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Abstract

The dynamic nature of science education demands innovative evaluation strategies that promote active learning and competence among pre-service teachers. Effective Biology practical hinge on the fact that teachers' proficiency in process skills. This paper proposes and explores the implementation of an "Instant Evaluation Strategy" (IES) for assessing future Biology teachers' mastery of these skills within practical exercises. IES involves real time evaluation of specific process skills displayed during practical activities and immediate feedback. This study discusses how IES assessments tools like rubrics, observation, checklist and digital feedback mechanism can enhance skill acquisition, reflection and pedagogical readiness. Potential benefits, limitation and challenges of IES were highlighted, and conclude with recommendation by advocating the integration of Instant Evaluation Strategy (IES) into Biology education programs to improve the effectiveness of Biology practical and overall teacher competence.

Keywords: Biology practical, pre-service, instant evaluation strategy, pedagogical, process skills, rubrics.

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Introduction

Biology as an empirical science relies on practical activities to foster understanding, enhance scientific thinking and develop essential process skills such as: experimentation, observation, measurement, data analysis and interpretation. These skills are crucial for students to develop a deep understanding of scientific concepts and to conduct scientific investigations (Klein, 2013). Practical experience is very fundamental in the teaching and learning of Biology. The practical aspect of any science course including Biology forms the building block for the technological developments. Practical activities lead to skill development and instill in students the confidence, for future academic pursuits in the subject. In spite of the importance of practical activities in science subjects, most teachers still resort to verbal presentation of facts. Nwagbo (2007) noted that most Biology teachers use all the biology periods for teaching the theoretical aspects of the subject neglecting the practical aspects which has the potential for developing critical thinking and scientific skills in students. This negligence and minimum practice of activity oriented-method in teaching Biology has led to abstraction, which makes the students less active and more involved in rote memorization. (Imanda, I.C.O., Omwenga, E., Andima, G. & Obuba, E. (2020) and Sadhana (2017)) was of the opinion that practical learning should be promoted and rote learning should be discouraged. The newly Biology curriculum from the Federal Ministry of Education (2008) emphasizes development of laboratory techniques and skills since Biology finds its application in agriculture, human and veterinary medicine to mention a few. Hence biology teachers in the 21st Century are doubly challenged. Most schools do not have laboratory personnel (attendants, technologies) that are saddled with the management of laboratory activities. Hence Biology teachers impact concepts in Biology and at the same time serves as a laboratory assistant or the likes.

Scientific process skills are skills that every individual could use in each step of his or her daily life by being scientifically literate and increasing the quality and standard of life by comprehending the nature of science. Using these skills, students not only gather new knowledge but also develop their understanding of scientific processes and methods which allow them to explore the surrounding world (Cipkova & Karolcik, 2018). Students need these skills as they use scientific reasoning and critical thinking to develop their understanding of science (Gillies & Nichols, 2015). In addition, the development of science process skills has a great influence on developing mental processes such as decision making and critical thinking (Tseng, Tuan, & Chin, (2013) and Shahali, Halim., Tregust, Won, & Chandrasegaran, (2017)). Process skills otherwise known as inquiry skills are essential for conducting scientific investigation are highly valued in the field of science education (Abd-El-Khalick & Lederman, 2000). Science process skills according to Aslan (2015) are not only important in preparing future scientist and technologists, but also for the whole population who need scientific literacy.

Assessment of scientific process skills

Many educators have written about science process skills or intellectual skills, or inquiry skill. The American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) identified some

scientific process skills and categorized them into two: basic and integrated (Science Community Representing Education, (SCORED), 2008) The basic science process skills comprise of: observing, inferring, measuring, communicating, classifying and predicting while the integrated science process skills comprise of: controlling variables, defining operationally, formulating variables, interpreting data, experimenting and formulating models. Assessment of these process skills, (Psychomotor) is as important as if not more important than assessment in the other domains of learning (cognitive and affective).

Assessment in teaching and learning is highly vital for tracking students learning progress and making informed decision (Rahman, Hassan, Namaziandost and Ibna Seraj, 2021 and Kikomelo, Luhanya and John, 2023). Without evaluation, teachers remain uncertain about how far students understand and whether or not they acquire the knowledge and skills they are intended to gain (Ombay, Kikomelo and Daniel, 2024). Evaluation helps us to determine the extent to which students have mastered the concepts taught and achieved learning objectives. Incidentally, assessment of science process skill has always been done through the traditional paper and pencil that cannot measure skill acquisition to any appreciable level of accuracy (Oloruntegbe and Omoifo, 2008).

However, several innovative evaluation strategies have been proposed by scholars to assess students' mastery of process skills, including peer assessment (Topping, 2010), self-assessment (Boud, 2013) and technology-enhanced assessment (Spector, 2014). Peer assessment involved students evaluating each other's work, providing feedback and guidance to improve performance. Self-assessment involves student evaluating their own work, reflecting on their strengths and weakness, and setting goals for improvement. Technology-enhanced assessment involves the use of digital tools and platforms to assess student learning, providing immediate feedback and opportunities for reflection. In addition, a number of instruments have been designed recently to measure these scientific process skills, which include test of Science Process Skills (TOSPS) developed by Oloruntegbe and Omoifo (2008) to measure scientific process skills in Junior Secondary 2 students. Although Gormally, Brickman and Lutz, (2012) point out that while a number of instruments have been developed to assess individual aspects of scientific literacy skills, there is no single instrument to measure all skills. Therefore, in the light of this, the instant evaluation strategy could be used in conjunction with paper and pencil test in assessing future teacher's mastery of process skills in Biology practical.

Instant Evaluation Strategy in Biology Evaluation

Biology as a core subject in science education plays a crucial role in shaping the scientific literacy and practical competence of learners. For pre-service teachers, Biology practical offer an essential platform to acquire and demonstrate scientific process skills necessary for effective teaching. Instant evaluation strategy which involves real-time, formative feedback mechanisms during instructional or practical activities, offers a promising alternative which lay emphasis on the entire process of learning and its outcomes thus aligning well with the demands of 21st century education. It can significantly enhance learning when effectively implemented.

The steps involved in IES strategy are:

1. Active monitoring of students by the instructor or lecturer during Biology practical classes to ascertain whether the students are doing the correct thing or not
2. Grading the students while carrying out process skills like observation, classification, focusing an object, drawing and dissection.
3. Giving immediate feedback to the students on their performance during practical class and making corrections on their weaknesses.

Implementation of Instant Evaluation Strategy (IES)

Instant evaluation strategy can be implemented through a structured approach within biology teacher education programs involving the following key components:

1. Clear learning objectives: Start by clearly defining the specific process skills that future teachers are expected to master during each practical activity. Examples include:
 - i. Observation: Accurately noting and describing observable phenomena
 - ii. Measurement: Using appropriate instrument and units to obtain accurate quantitative data
 - iii. Data recording: Organizing and presenting data effectively in tables, graphic and charts
 - iv. Data analysis: Identify patterns, trends and relationships with the data
 - v. Interpretation: Drawing logical conclusion and explaining findings based on evidence
 - vi. Experiment design: Planning and executing experiments using appropriate controls and variables
2. Structured observation checklists and rubrics: Develop specific observation checklist and rubrics for each practical activity, outlining the criteria for assessing each process skill. These tools should be:
 - i. Specific and measurable: Clearly define what constitutes proficient performance of each skill
 - ii. Behaviorally focused: Describe behaviors that demonstrate mastery of the skill
 - iii. Diagnostic: Provide specific information about strengths and weakness
 - iv. Immediate feedback and guidance: During practical activity, instructors actively observe future teachers using the checklist and rubrics to provide immediate feedback on their performance. The feedback should be:
 - i. Specific and constructive: This highlight both strengths and areas for improvement
 - ii. Timely: The feedback should be provided immediately after observing the skill being demonstrated, maximizing its impact
 - iii. Actionable: It should provide specific suggestions for how the future teachers can improve their skills
4. Focused formative assessments: Incorporate short, focused formative assessments such as mini quizzes, quick demonstration throughout the practical session to assess understanding of key concepts and procedures.
5. Peer evaluation and self-reflection: Encourage future teachers to evaluate each other's performance using the same checklist and rubrics. This promotes critical thinking and self-reflection on their performance

6. Remedial activities: Based on the feedback and assessment results, provide targeted remedial activities to address specific weakness. This may involve:
- Focused practice: Providing additional opportunities to practice specific skills
 - Demonstration and modeling: Instructors demonstrating the correct techniques
 - Peer Tutoring: This is pairing pre-service teachers who have mastered a skill with those who need more attention and support.

Benefits of Implementing Instant Evaluation Strategy

The use of instant evaluation strategy in assessing pre-service teachers' process skills in biology practical has been supported by several studies. Chan (2015) reported that the use of a checklist during Biology practical improved pre-service teachers' performance in process skills. Similarly, Abdulwaheed and Acton (2016) found that the use of rubric to evaluate pre-service teachers' performance during biology practical promoted their understanding and application of process skills. Instant evaluation strategy has several benefits including improved student learning outcomes, increased students' engagement and enhanced teacher feedback (Topping, 2010, Boud, 2013, Spector, 2014).

1. Improved mastery of process skills: It provides a focused and targeted approach to skill development, leading to deeper understanding and improved competence in conducting Biology practical.
2. Increased confidence and self-efficacy: Immediate feedback can significantly boost pre-service teachers' confidence and competence in their ability to conduct practical biology effectively.
3. Enhanced pedagogical skills: Analyzing their own performance and receiving feedback on their practical activities helps pre-service teachers develop pedagogical skills in the content of practical activities.
4. Well Equipped pre-service Teachers: Well-equipped and confident pre-service teacher are equipped effectively to design and conduct engaging and hand-on-minds-on biology practical for their future students.
5. Prompt identification of Weaknesses: Instant evaluation strategy allows for early identification of weaknesses in process skill, allowing for timely intervention and as well preventing these weaknesses from becoming ingrained habit.
6. Data-Driven Instruction: The data collected through checklists, rubrics and formative assessments can be used to inform instructional decisions and tailor the curriculum to meet the specific needs for pre-service biology teachers.
7. Autonomy and Accountability: Instant evaluation strategy enhanced learner's autonomy and accountability of their actions and performance in Biology practical activities.

Limitation and Challenges

1. Time Constraints: Implementing instant evaluation strategy effectively requires significant time for observation, feedback and remediation especially in large class settings.

2. Subjectivity in Evaluation: There is potential for bias in observational assessments although checklists and rubrics can help in reducing subjectivity.
3. Instructor Training: Instructors needs to be properly trained on how to use instant evaluation strategy effectively to provide constructive feedback and implement remedial activities.
4. Resource Requirements: Developing and implementing instant evaluation techniques may require additional resources such as checklists, rubrics and remedial materials.
5. Resistance from pre-service Teachers: Some future teachers may be resistant to immediate feedback, especially if it is perceived as critical or judgmental.

Implications for Confidence and Competence for Effective Conduct of Biological Practical

1. Enhanced Instructional Quality: Teachers trained using instant evaluation strategy is more likely to implement similar practices in their classrooms, learning to better teaching practices.
2. Curriculum Alignment: Modern science curricula emphasize inquiry and process-oriented learning. Instant evaluation strategy aligns well with these goals, making them valuable for teacher preparation programs.
3. Improved Learning Outcomes: Immediate feedback allows learners to reflect and adjust during biology practical which enhances learning and reflection.

Conclusion

The 'Instant Evaluation Strategy offers a promising approach to enhancing pre-service Biology teachers' mastery of process skills in practical activities. By providing immediate feedback, targeted remediation, and opportunities for self-reflection, instant evaluation strategy can significantly boost confidence, improved competence and engaging Biology practical for their future students. While challenges related to time constraints, subjectively and instructors training need to be addressed. By embracing this innovative approach, Biology teacher education programs can better equip future teachers with adequate skills and knowledge necessary to inspire the next generation of scientists.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are crucial for successful integration of Instant Evaluation Strategy into Biology teacher education programs.

1. Pilot Testing: Conduct pilot testing of Instant Evaluation Strategy with a small group of pre-service Biology teachers to identify and address any potential challenges before implementing it on a larger scale.
2. Instructor Training: Comprehensive training should be provided for instructors on how to use Instant Evaluation Strategy effectively.
3. Clear Communication: Instructors should clearly communicate the purpose of Instant Evaluation Strategy to future Biology teachers and emphasize its focus on supporting their learning and development in scientific process skills.

4. Positive Reinforcement: Positive reinforcement should be stressed and also highlight pre-service teachers' strength and weakness through immediate constructive feedback.
5. Effective use of Technology: explore the use of technology effectively to streamline the evaluation process such as mobile apps for data collection and feedback delivery
6. Continuous Evaluation and Refinement: There should be continuous evaluation of effectiveness of Instant Evaluation Strategy and make adjustments based on feedback from instructors and pre-service teachers.

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